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CLASH OF NATURE, CULTURE AND SCIENCE IN MAHESH DATTANI’ S PLAY, TARA

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ABSTRACT

Mahesh Dattani’s play, Tara, has often been discussed in relation to feminism. But on closer inspection it communicates much deeper conflict than mere feminism. In one of his interviews Mahesh Dattani said, ‘... it’s a play about the self, about the man and the woman in self, but a lot of people think of it as a play about the girl child’ (Mee, 1997: 21). The play indeed dramatizes, chiefly through the character of Dr. Thakkar whose presence on the stage is almost consistent, the subtle conflict between scientific temper and cultural notations of life. This paper intends to focus the dramatic significance of his role in the given setting, both thematic and demonstrative, with a view to doing justice to his characterization which has been denied so far in academic discourses. The relationship of scientific advancement and cultural progress has been probed into with this very critical intention.

Keywords: Feminism, Culture, Science, Nature

Introduction

Mahesh Dattani is a prolific Indian theatre artist, a well-established playwright, a stage director and a script writer, and a filmmaker. He is the first Indian playwright who won the prestigious Sahitya Academy award for his *Final Solutions and Other Plays* in 1998. He has established himself internationally by writing plays for BBC Radio and other international collaborations. Mahesh Dattani can be placed among the most successful Indian stage-directors and dramatists whose plays brought him immediate success and recognition in India and abroad. His important plays are *Where There’s a Will* (1986), *Dance Like a Man* (1989), *Tara* (1990), *Bravely Fought the Queen* (1991), *Final Solutions* (1993), *Do the Needful* (1997), *On a Muggy Night in Mumbai* (1998), *Seven Steps Around the Fire* (1999), *The Murder That Never Was* (2000), *30 Days in September* (2001), *Brief Candle* (2009), *Where Did I Leave My Purda* (2012) and *The Big Fat City* (2012). He started his own theatre company, named Playpen, in 1984. Mahesh Dattani’s debut film is *Mango Souffle*, adapted from one of his plays. He has also written and directed the movie *Morning Raaga*.

Unusual love relationships, homosexuality, exploitation of women, incest and child-sex abuse and communal disharmony, have been the central issues of Mahesh Dattani’s works. According to Kumar (2014), ‘He, in his plays, keeps women at the center of his dramatic world and may be called an avant-garde feminist’ (Kumar, 2014, 360). Tripathi and Kumari also support Kumar’s views. They have written, ‘He has the courage to discuss unconventional themes like homosexuality, men pursuing dance as career, pain and suffering of conjoined twins, and child sexual abuse’ (Tripathi and Kumari. 2007: 20). About the thematic aspects of Mahesh Dattani’s plays Trehan (2016) stipulates:

He takes the family unit as the locus of most of his plays focusing on human relationships and personal choices representing contemporary people with their predicaments and complexities, joy and anguish which are the classic concerns of world drama.

(Trehan, 2016: 63)

Mahesh Dattani tries to address contemporary social issues with the help of Indian mythology, rituals and traditions and tries to uncover the deep-rooted biases and prejudices (especially against the marginalized section of society, like minorities, women, gays, and eunuch), and problems that Indian society always tries to hide, for example his plays like, *Bravely Fought the Queen*, *On a Muggy Night in Mumbai*, *Seven Steps Around the Fire*, etc. According to Joshipura (2009), Dattani's plays:

...principally deal with humanism in general and injustice to marginalized section of society such as homosexuals, hijras and women, in particular. In all of them, he provokes our thinking, compels us to think afresh about the problems... and to change our conventional attitudes and assumptions about what is right and what is wrong, what is good and what is evil.

(Joshipura, 2009: 01),

Some studies like Chakrabarti (2009), Mishra (2009), Iyer (2009), and Sinha (2009) also support how Mahesh Dattani's Plays challenge heterosexual behavior, the only socially acceptable sexual orientation, generally considered as dominant to Indian culture. These studies talk about the suffering and trauma of homosexual people.

Tara, one of the most popular plays of Mahesh Dattani, deals with the different dimension of human relationships with reference to Indian culture. It provides a socio-psychological analysis of gender identity and gendered self. According to Kumar (2009) 'In critical ambit Tara, a play is neither a saga of Chandan's alienation nor Tara's death albeit, it is a tragic tale of the patriarchal society which is bruised by gender preference' (Kumar, 2009: 123). Mahesh Dattani's play, Tara, has often been much discussed in relation to feminism and issues related to gender. If we take into the thematic aspects of the play, no doubt it deals with feminism. It does not simply talk about gender inequality rather it talks about the diagnostic of gender inequality in our society. It seems Mahesh Dattani tries to suggest how females, to an extent, are responsible for their subordinate stature in society. One of the themes of the play is about the acceptance of male chauvinism and dominance by female. This idea has been communicated by Mahesh Dattani through the character of Bharati Patel.

No doubt the play, Tara has many layers of interpretations. On closer inspection it communicates much deeper conflict than mere feminism and issues related to gender. It has often been observed that the character of Dr. Thakkar is given relatively less priority whenever we try to analyze the plot of the play. The dramatic significance of his role in the given setting, if not ignored, has often been not highlighted. The character of Dr. Thakkar has some symbolic significance in the play. He represents the rapid scientific advancement of the second half of the twentieth century. In other words, it can be said that he is a by-product of the modern technological advancement and industrialization who, to some extent, failed to cope up with the prevalent societal ethics and values. He is the integral part of the plot since it is his unethical decision which brings/adds suffering to Tara, The tragedy of Tara could have been avoided, if Dr. Thakkar had observed the medical ethics.

It is difficult to ignore the medical condition of the twin that is central to the plot of the play. It is an integral part of the story. Dattani himself has said that the play is about a conjoined twin, the only literary liberty he has taken is he made the twin (medically of the same sex) into a male and a female. There is no doubt that with the help of the conjoined twin Dattani wants to communicate how males and females are two different but inseparable entities of our society (Banerjee and Dattani, 2004: 163). If they are separated by any unethical (social) practice, it would be a threat to their survival. However, the conjoined twin may also be symbolically interpreted as the mutual relationship between science and humanities or culture.

Now let us look into some of the empirical evidences from the text to support our hypothesis (one of the central ideas of Mahesh Dattani's Play, Tara is to show clash of culture and science). Mahesh Dattani said that he writes plays because he is a person deeply attached to theatre not vice versa. In other words we can say that he primarily writes plays to be staged. Stage settings play a decisive role to interpret his plays. Therefore, it would be logical to, first of all, to take into account the stage settings and stage direction of the play, Tara. In the description of the stage setting it is written that Dr. Thakkar has been given the higher level of the stage.

Extract 1

Behind, on a higher level, is a chair in which Dr. Thakkar remains seated throughout the play". Although he does not watch the action of the play, his connection is asserted by his sheer God-like presence

(Tara, 2000: 323)

Mahesh Dattani tries to portray the Character of Dr. Thakkar as a doctor who has God-like stance – may be as a creator and destroyer. It shows his control and power. In order to show his dominance and control in the plot he has been given the higher level on the stage. He is the representative of the modern science and technology which plays a crucial role in the contemporary society. Like science and technology which seems does not directly influence our relationships, he does not watch the action of the play but he is an integral part of it. In order to further emphasize his importance, Dattani decides to make the character of Dr. Thakkar remain seated throughout the play.

Extract II

"Chandan and Tara walk into it. They both have a limp, but on a different legs"

(Tara, 2000: 324)

The play begins with an assertion and claim of Chandan (who has been addressed as Dan whenever he has been shown in London for convenience and dramatic significance) that despite separation from Tara, he still feels firmly attached to her. He also accepts and assesses that his 'progress ... has been zero' after the separation. It seems quite obvious that Mahesh Dattani wants to communicate more than what the above extract literary means. It has layers of metaphorical meanings. We can interpret this statement as a keen observation of Mahesh Dattani about the contemporary society. One twin (it seems Chandan) seemsto represents scientific progress while the other represents the social and cultural advancement. It may be interpreted here that despite huge scientific and social advancement, one can observe an imbalance and lack of coordination between them. The problem lies both in the cultural advancement and the scientific and technological progress. However, the nature of problems differs in both the cases. In order to ensure a balanced overall inclusive development and growth, the scientific and technological progress should be made in consonance with cultural advancement and vice versa. The paly basically deals with medical science and unethical medical practice of a doctor. It highlights some fo the hidden aspects of medical practice. There are many things that do not come into the public domain.

Extract III

Bhartai: No! I don't want any children being mentioned in any of medical journal!

(Tara, 2000: 326)

Bharati, Mother of Tara, does not want Tara to be discussed in one of the medical journals. Even if the rare critical medical condition of Tara is discussed in a medical journal, the unethical surgery of Dr. Thakkar will not be discussed. There are many unethical medical practices that never go out in public domain. In his interview, Dr. Thakkar says, 'But the important thing is ... the separation was a complete success' (Tara, 2000: 375). He, in the end of the interview, cunningly tries to hide his criminal activity and he accuses nature for being harsh to Tara. To quote Dr. Thakkar, 'Our greatest challenge would be keep the girl alive. Nature wanted to kill her. We couldn't allow it' (Tara, 2000: 376). The first sentence he utters here is a fact that due to unethical surgery Tara's life was critical. The rest two sentences of his utterance are also fact in terms of proposition but He

interchanges the agents. It was not nature rather that 'we' (Dr. Thakkar, Bharati and her father) who wanted to kill her to save Chandan).

Extract IV

Conflict is the crux of life. A duel to the death between God and nature on one side and on the other – the amazing Dr. Thakkar. (Smiles)

(Tara, 2000: 330)

Apparently it seems that one of the thematic aspects of the play is how science and nature are complementary to each other. If any attempt is made to challenge the laws of nature, there would be a conflict and consequently disaster. The character of Dr. Thakkar tries to separate the twin against the way nature has biologically programmed the twin. However, it was not the fault of medical science; it was unethical and criminal medical practice of Dr. Thakkar that was responsible for the tragedy. This statement of Dan (Chandan) is an example of a verbal irony. He addresses Dr. Thakkar with the adjective 'amazing'. If we take into account the character of Dr. Thakkar, he is an example of situational irony. One of the fundamental objectives of medical science and a doctor is to save human lives but what happens in the play is almost just opposite. However, Medically Dr. Thakkar is very competent but somewhere he lacks the required values and ethics to be a good doctor. In other words, he educated himself properly in terms of medical science but he fails to receive the cultural and moral values that is required to be a good doctor. Dan introduces Dr. Thakkar in a "mock" television interview as an outstanding doctor with international repute (Tara, 2000: 331).

Extract V

But, soon, even the remotest chance for survival was received with hope once they were made aware of the facilities offer by modern technology. ... there was a strong possibility of both twin surviving.

(Tara, 2000: 342)

The above extract convinces us that all the test reports of the twin before the surgery were in favor of their survival. Theoretically, the modern medical technology and facility were sufficient to successfully separate the conjoined twin with help of a surgery. To quote Dr. Thakkar, 'Nature had done a near complete job. Medical science could finish it for her' (Tara, 2000: 356). There was nothing wrong as long as Dr. Thakkar practiced his medical science knowledge in consonance with ethics. As Dr. Thakkar says, 'there was [is] a strong possibility of both the twin surviving'. In the same way, science, culture and nature have the potential to coexist and complement one another. He boasts of the new technology and findings of medical science. He says:

Extract VI

Dr. Thakkar: Yes, indeed, it was a complex case. But modern technology has made many things possible, we are not very far from the rest of the world, In fact, in ten years' time we should be on par with the best in the west

Dan's area is lit. He applauds mockingly.

(Tara, 2000: 379)

It is not only Dr. Thakkar who is a byproduct of imbalance and disproportionate developed culture but also some other characters like, Bharati and his father. The story of the play is not about illiterate or uneducated people. It is about the people who belong to the highest class of the society who almost always claim to be quite cultured and civilized. They are called modern people who do not believe in any orthodox and conservative practice of society. Both Bharati and his father are equally responsible for the unethical surgery of the twin and for the suffering of Tara.

Conclusion:- The play seems quite relevant in the twenty-first century where the scientific progress in general and medical education and practice in particular needs to address some of the issues in order to adapt with cultural progress and nature. It has been observed that service provided by doctors, especially in India, is rarely

challenged and questions by common people. We seldom negotiate and bargain with a doctor. We do not question them because, may be, the faith we have or/and we are ignorant about the discipline.

With the help of the data we have analyzed so far, it seems that the hypothesis is proved. Almost all the extracts we have analyzed and interpreted here suggest one of the thematic aspects of the play, Tara is to depict a clash and imbalance between scientific advancement, and nature and culture. The play indeed dramatizes, chiefly through the character of Dr. Thakkar the subtle conflict between scientific temper and cultural notations of life. The play depicts a sort of imbalance between Natural science and Social Science. The play also deals with duel between science and nature. Probably the clash and mutual dependency of science and culture has also been communicated with the help of the twin. A good and wealthy society can be imagine only when there is a balance, harmony and coordination between Science and Humanities.

The play hints that the cultural development in our society has not taken place with the same pace as science and technology has progressed. Cultural development has almost always been given relatively less priorities in comparison to scientific development. Sometimes we not ready to adapt ourselves according to the social change brought by scientific advancement. Another offshoot of this discussion is nature and environment. Nature and environment, like culture, has also been less prioritized in comparison to science. It seems Mahesh Dattani warns us that in the end the culture and nature may leave us alone like Chandan left his father all alone.

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